

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MUCOADHESIVE TABLETS OF PROPRANOLOL HCL USING BIOPOLYMERS

Patil N. D.¹, *Patil K.S.¹, Marathe R. P.²

¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Government College of Pharmacy, Kathora Naka, Amravati, Maharashtra- 444604, India.

²Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Government College of Pharmacy, Aurangabad, Maharashtra-431005, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 11/06/2018

Available online

28/08/2018

Keywords

Biopolymer,
Mucoadhesion,
Swelling,
Diffusion,
Stability.

ABSTRACT

Natural material and polymers are used as an agent for sustaining the release of different drugs. These substances when comes in contact with water, get hydrated and adhere to mucosa. The present study is aimed at formulation of sustained release mucoadhesive tablet of propranolol HCl using Cordia and Bael mucilage in comparison to HPMC. Propranolol HCl was selected as a model drug, as it has short biological half life hence requires frequent dosing. Wet granulation method was employed for preparation of tablets and prepared tablets were evaluated for weight variation, hardness, friability, drug content, swelling index, erosion study, *in-vitro* drug release and *in-vitro* mucoadhesion study. All formulations showed compliance with official standards. Swelling indices are increased with an increase in concentration of the biopolymers whereas erosion showed dependence on nature and concentration of polymer. Mucoadhesive strength was highest for batch F9(28.15±0.65) and lowest for F4(14.91±0.43). Amongst all formulations, F₃ exhibited highest percentage of release i.e. 97.12±2.47% in 12 h as well as satisfactory results for other evaluation parameters hence designated as optimized batch. The release kinetics of optimized formulation F₃ was best fitted in zero order kinetics. The 'n' value for Korsmeyer-Peppas equation was 1.057 revealed that the release mechanism was super case II. Optimized formulation F₃ was kept for stability study according to ICH guideline, which showed insignificant change in *in-vitro* drug release and other evaluation parameters hence found stable.

Corresponding author

Dr. K. S. Patil,

Department of Pharmaceutics,
Government College of Pharmacy,
Kathora Naka, Amravati,
Maharashtra- 444604, India.
kundan_patil36@rediffmail.com
9421918049

Please cite this article in press as Patil N. D et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Mucoadhesive Tablets of Propranolol HCl using Biopolymers. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2018:8(08).

Copy right © 2018 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Oral drug delivery continues to rise in popularity as formulation scientists look for ways to control drug release and improve patient convenience.[1] Over the last 50 years, as the expense and complication involved in marketing new drug entities have increased, with concomitant recognition of the therapeutic advantages of controlled drug delivery, greater attention has been focus on the development of sustain or controlled-release drug delivery system.[2] Mucoadhesive delivery system have several advantages by virtue of prolongation of residence time, drug targeting, intimate contact between dosage form and the absorptive mucosa. Mucoadhesive formulations use polymers as the adhesive component. These polymers are often water soluble and when used in a dry form, they attract water from the mucosal surface and this water transfer leads to a strong interaction further increasing the retention time over the mucosal surfaces and leads to adhesive interactions.[3]

Gums and mucilages are widely used natural materials for conventional and novel dosage forms. These natural materials have advantages over synthetic ones since they are chemically inert, nontoxic, less expensive, biodegradable and widely available. They can also be modified in different ways to obtain tailor-made materials for drug delivery systems and thus can compete with the available synthetic excipients.[4-7] So the aim of present research work was to formulate and evaluate mucoadhesive drug delivery system using mucilage obtained from natural mucilage material.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials

Propranolol HCl was obtained as a gift sample from Quantum Drug and Chemical, Mumbai, India. HPMC K15M was obtained as a gift sample from Colorcon Asia Pvt Ltd, Verna, Goa. Lactose, Magnesium stearate was purchased from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai. Natural mucilages were extracted as from fruits of *Cordia latifolia* (Cordia) and *Aegle marmelos* (Bael) by aqueous extraction method.[8]

Methods

Preparation of Tablets:

Tablets were prepared by wet granulation method. Drug and excipients were weighed accurately as per composition given in **Table No 1** and thoroughly mixed to obtain uniform mixing. Then required quantity of warm water was added to the powder and mixed thoroughly to form damp mass. Then prepared damp mass was passed through sieve no # 16 and retained on sieve no. #22 and granules were dried in hot air oven at 50-60°C. Then dried granules evaluated for true density, angle of repose, bulk density and Carr's index. The dried granules were lubricated with magnesium stearate and compressed into tablets using rotary tablet compression machine(Cadmach, Ahmedabad). The prepared tablets were subjected to evaluation.[9]

Table No 1: Composition of Propranolol HCl Tablets:

Ingredients (mg)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆	F ₇	F ₈	F ₉
Propranolol HCl	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Cordia mucilage	100	125	150	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bael mucilage	-	-	-	100	125	150	-	-	-
HPMC	-	-	-	-	-	-	100	125	150
Lactose	105	80	55	105	80	55	105	80	55
Magnesium stearate (2%)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

*All the ingredients are represented in mg and are given for one tablet.

Characterization of Granules:

Prepared granules were characterized for different physical parameter such as bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio. [10,11] Results are as shown in Table No. 2.

Table No 2: Physical Properties of Granules.

Batch	Bulk density(g/cc)	Tapped density (g/cc)	Angle of repose	Carr's index	Hausner's ratio
F ₁	0.49	0.594	21 ⁰ 31'	17.50	1.21
F ₂	0.485	0.581	23 ⁰ 18'	16.52	1.19
F ₃	0.473	0.573	24 ⁰ 45'	17.45	1.21
F ₄	0.485	0.598	22 ⁰ 54'	18.89	1.23
F ₅	0.471	0.574	23 ⁰ 17'	17.94	1.21
F ₆	0.457	0.565	24 ⁰ 58'	19.11	1.23
F ₇	0.493	0.601	20 ⁰ 41'	17.97	1.21
F ₈	0.486	0.591	21 ⁰ 44'	17.76	1.21
F ₉	0.479	0.577	23 ⁰ 06'	16.98	1.20

Evaluation of Tablets: [10-14]**Weight Variation:**

Twenty tablets were randomly selected from each batch and individually weighed. The average weight and standard deviation of 20 tablets was calculated.

Hardness:

Three samples were selected randomly from each batch and hardness was measured using Campbell digital tablet tester. (Model No. C – WWTDH 500 N)

Friability:

Twenty tablets were weighed and placed in the Roche friabilator and tablets were rotated at 25rpm for 4 minutes. After revolutions the tablets were de-dusted and weighed again. The percentage friability was calculated using following formula.

$$\% F = \{1 - (W / W_0)\} \times 100$$

Where,

%F = friability in percentage, W_0 = Initial weight of tablets, W = Weight of tablets after revolution.

Thickness and Diameter:

Three samples were selected randomly from each batch and thickness was measured using Campbell digital tablet tester (Model No. C-WWTDH 500 N). Similarly three tablets from each batch were tested for diameter.

Drug Content:

One tablet from each batch was randomly selected and powdered in a mortar. An accurately weighed material 100 mg quantity of powdered tablet transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask and 70 ml of acid buffer pH 1.2 was added to it. It was shaken occasionally for about 30 min and volume was made upto 100ml with acid buffer pH 1.2. The obtained solution was filtered through 0.45 μ Whatman filter paper and suitably diluted and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 288.2 nm. The test was repeated three times (n=3) for each batch of tablets. [9]

Table No 3: Post Compression Parameter of Propranolol HCl Tablets.

Formulations	Hardness* (kg/cm ²)	Friability* (%w/w)	Thickness* (mm)	Diameter* (mm)	% Drug Content*
F ₁	4.35±0.38	0.48±0.05	2.74±0.22	8.03±0.02	97.95±2.29
F ₂	4.53±0.51	0.35±0.04	2.61±0.35	8.01±0.01	98.90±3.30
F ₃	4.71±0.36	0.31±0.04	2.60±0.36	8.02±0.03	98.52± 1.53
F ₄	4.22±0.43	0.46±0.02	2.81±0.41	8.02±0.02	96.32±3.14
F ₅	4.54±0.33	0.32±0.04	2.77±0.37	8.01±0.02	99.15±2.10
F ₆	4.89±0.52	0.24±0.05	2.62±0.38	8.01±0.03	98.32±1.87
F ₇	4.96±0.47	0.41±0.02	2.54±0.42	8.03±0.01	96.65±3.19
F ₈	5.34±0.42	0.32±0.03	2.41±0.35	8.02±0.03	95.57±4.59
F ₉	5.52±0.54	0.23±0.04	2.37±0.36	8.03±0.02	98.90±0.09

*Each value represents mean (n=3) ± SD.

Swelling and Erosion Study: [15-17]

The extent of swelling was studied % weight gain method. One tablet from each formulation was kept in a petri dish containing pH 1.2 for 2 h and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer for 6 h. At the end of 0.5 h and 1 h, the tablet was withdrawn, soaked with tissue paper, and weighed. Then after every 1 h, weights of the tablet were noted, and the process was till the end of 8 h. To determine matrix erosion, tablet was introduced into the dissolution apparatus under the standard set of conditions as specified for determination of *in vitro* drug release. The tablets were removed using a small basket at hourly intervals and swollen tablets were placed in an oven at 40°C and after 48 h tablets were removed and weighed. The same tablet was subjected for erosion study up to 12 h. Swelling (%) and erosion (%) was calculated according to the following formula,

$$\% \text{ Swelling} = (W_t - W_0) / W_0 \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ Erosion} = (W_0 - W_r) / W_0 \times 100$$

Where, W_t = the weight of the matrix after swelling

W_0 = the initial weight of the matrix

W_r = the weight of the eroded matrix

Figure 3: Percentage Swelling Indices of Formulations F₁ – F₉.

Figure 4: Percentage Erosion of Formulations F₁-F₉.

Figure 1: FTIR Spectra of pure Propranolol HCl.

Figure 2: FTIR Spectra of formulation F₃.

Mucoadhesion study: [18-20]

Mucoadhesive strength was determined by using modified physical balance method, for which Goat stomach mucosa was collected from local slaughter house and stored in Krebs solution. Mucosa was stucked on glass slide using double sided sticker which was already stucked on the bottom of 100 ml beaker, and this beaker was placed in 1 Ltr beaker which already contained 0.1N HCl of pH 1.2. Tablet were stucked on lower side of left pan of double pan balance using double sided sticker, in both pan of the balance empty beaker were placed and their weight were adjusted, near to the right sided pan arrangement of burette were made for drop wise addition of water, as shown in figure . The mucosal and tablet surface was wetted with few drop of 0.1N HCl and on the left pan tablet 5 gm weight was placed for 5min. to allow the initial contact of mucoadhesion. Then drop wise water was added in beaker of right pan till the detachment of tablet from the mucous membrane was observed. Then weight of water present in right pan beaker was determined, using following formula.

$$\text{Mucoadhesive strength} = (\text{Wt. of the beaker} + \text{Wt. of the water}) - \text{Wt. of the empty beaker.}$$

After determination of mucoadhesive strength Force of adhesion was calculated using formula:

$$\text{Force of adhesion (N)} = \text{Mucoadhesive strength} \times 9.81 / 100$$

Table No. 4: Mucoadhesion force of different formulations.

Code	Mucoadhesive Strength(g)	Mucoadhesion Force (N)
F ₁	19.61±0.54	1.92±0.13
F ₂	21.73±0.67	2.13±0.11
F ₃	24.08±0.39	2.36±0.10
F ₄	14.91±0.43	1.46±0.08
F ₅	16.49±0.71	1.62±0.09
F ₆	17.32±0.57	1.70±0.12
F ₇	23.77±0.48	2.33±0.14
F ₈	25.41±0.89	2.49±0.12
F ₉	28.15±0.65	2.76±0.15

*Each value represents mean (n=3) ± SD.

In-vitro release study:

The *in vitro* drug release study was performed using USP type II dissolution apparatus (Dissolution Test Apparatus, Model DA-3, Veego Scientific Devices, Mumbai). Dissolution of tablets was carried out in acid buffer pH 1.2 for 12 h at 37 ± 0.5° C and 50 rpm speed at 100 rpm. Samples were collected at every 1 hour interval and replaced with an equal volume of fresh medium in order to maintain volume. The collected samples were sufficiently diluted and analyzed by using UV-visible spectrophotometer (Model. UV 2401 PC, Shimadzu Corporation, Singapore) at 288.2 nm. [9, 10]

Drug Release Kinetics

Drug release kinetics was assumed to reflect different release mechanisms of controlled release drug delivery systems. Therefore, kinetic treatment was applied to data obtained with zero order, first order, Higuchi, Korsmeyer's and Peppas's equations to find the best fitting equation.

Stability Study

The formulation F3 was wrapped in aluminium foil of thickness 0.04 mm subjected to stability studies as per the ICH guidelines at 40±2°C/75 ± 5% RH for 6 months. At an interval of 2 month, the tablets were subjected to physical properties, hardness, friability, drug content and *in vitro* drug release. [21]

DISCUSSION:**FTIR Study**

The presence of incompatibility between drug and biopolymers was evaluated by FTIR spectral study. FTIR of the propranolol HCl and different biopolymers used in formulation were characterized by FT-IR to check compatibility as shown in Figure 1 & 2. FTIR spectrums confirmed the presences of all prominent peaks at wave numbers 3278.76 cm⁻¹ (Secondary NH Stretching), 3053.11 cm⁻¹ (Aromatic CH stretching), 2964.39 cm⁻¹ and 2837 cm⁻¹ (Aliphatic asymmetric and symmetric C-H stretching), 1577.66 cm⁻¹ (N-H deformation) , 1456.16 cm⁻¹ (C-H deformation), 1107.06 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C structure) indicating its compatibility in presence of biopolymers.

Preparation of Tablets:

Propranolol HCl have proper flowability and compressibility desired for direct compression but when tablets were prepared by direct compression, the tablets were not exhibit sufficient strength and were more friable hence wet granulation method was employed for formulation of tablets.

Evaluation of Granules:

The prepared granules were evaluated for bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio, results are shown in Table No 2. The bulk density was in the range of 0.457 ± 0.014 to 0.493 ± 0.010 ; tapped density was in the range of 0.565 ± 0.017 to 0.601 ± 0.021 and angle of repose in the range of $21^{\circ}31' \pm 1.71$ to $24^{\circ}58' \pm 1.42$ which indicates excellent flow properties of granules of all formulations desired for tableting. Carr's index and Housner's ratio were found in the range of 16.52 ± 0.79 to 19.11 ± 0.93 and 1.19 ± 0.03 to 1.23 ± 0.04 respectively. The overall physical properties of granules were good and suitable for compression of granules into tablet.

Evaluation of Tablets:

Physicochemical Evaluation:

The prepared tablets using biopolymers were off-white, flat spherical shaped and smooth in appearance. The results of evaluation are shown in Table No.3. The average thickness of the tablets was found between 2.37 ± 0.36 – 2.81 ± 0.41 mm. The hardness of the tablets ranges from 4.22 ± 0.43 kg to 5.52 ± 0.54 kg. The % Friability was ranged between $0.23 \pm 0.04\%$ to $0.48 \pm 0.05\%$; which is an indication of good mechanical resistance of the tablets. The weight variation test was complies with official specification as per I. P. The drug content in each tablet was found to be within acceptable range $96.32 \pm 3.14\%$ to $99.15 \pm 2.10\%$.

Swelling and Erosion study:

Swelling index was performed for all the batches (F1-F9) for 8 hrs. It was found that swelling indices are directly proportional to the concentration of the biopolymer, as the biopolymer concentration increases there is increase in the swelling index. Thus, the viscosity of the gum had major influence on swelling process, matrix integrity, as well as adhesion property. Graphical representation of swelling index of all the batches is shown in Figure 3.

The formulations containing HPMC(F7,F8,F9) exhibit higher swelling whereas formulations containing bael mucilage(F4,F5,F6) showed least swelling may be due to more hydrophilic nature of HPMC which allows the matrix to absorb higher amount of water.

Erosion behavior was studied for all the batches (F1-F9) for 12 hrs and from results it can be concluded that erosion showed dependence on nature and concentration of polymer. The erosion was faster in F1 and slower in F9. It may be due to stability of polymer at gastric conditions. Graphical representation of % erosion is as shown in Figure 4.

Mucoadhesion study:

The results of mucoadhesion for F1-F9 are as shown in Table No. 5. The results suggested that, mucoadhesion strength and force showed dependence on nature and concentration of polymer. Mucoadhesive strength was highest for batch F9(28.15 ± 0.65) and lowest for F4(14.91 ± 0.43). Cordia mucilage exhibited comparable mucoadhesion as that of HPMC whereas bael mucilage was showed least mucoadhesive strength.

In-vitro release study:

In vitro dissolution study indicates that the release of Propranolol HCl varied according to the type and concentration of matrix forming natural material. The release of Propranolol HCl from various formulations containing natural mucilage was as per following order.

HPMC < Cordia mucilage < Bael mucilage

Figure 5: *In vitro* Drug Release Profiles of Formulations F₁ – F₉ for 12 h.

With increasing concentration of mucilage, the drug release decreases, as formation of sticky film of hydration on the surface of tablet reduces diffusion of drug. A comparative dissolution profile showed that, with an increase in concentration of mucilage release of drug from tablet decreased. From formulations F₁ to F₃ prepared using Cordia mucilage, formulations F₁ and F₂ shows highest percentage of release of Propranolol HCl (93.28 ± 1.25% and 95.97 ± 2.23% resp.) in 9 and 10 h respectively because it may contains insufficient amount of mucilage (100 mg and 125 mg resp.) which cannot sustain the release up to 12 h. As, these two formulations i.e. F₁ and F₂ shows the release of Propranolol HCl in 9 and 10 h therefore, these two formulations were rejected. Formulation F₃ sustained release of Propranolol HCl (97.12 ± 2.47 %) upto 12 h in comparison to F₁ and F₂.

From formulations F₄ to F₆ prepared using bael mucilage, formulations F₄, F₅ and F₆ exhibited highest percentage release of Propranolol HCl (92.11±2.89%, 96.98±2.54% and 94.33 ±3.89% resp.) in 8, 10 and 11h respectively because it contains insufficient amount of mucilage (100mg, 125mg and 150mg resp.) which unable to sustain release up to 12 h. Formulations F₄, F₅ and F₆ sustained the release of Propranolol HCl only upto 8, 10 and 11h respectively. Further it was observed that, formulations containing bael mucilage has ability to hydrate rapidly as compare to the Cordia mucilage and HPMC. The diffusional path length for bael mucilage was therefore smaller than other biopolymers, this may due to less gel thickness and faster erosion of the surface.

In the next part of experimentation three formulations F₇-F₉ were formulated using established polymer HPMC for comparison. Formulations F₇, F₈ and F₉ exhibited percentage release of Propranolol HCl 76.47±2.29%, 73.69±2.42% and 69.56±2.32% in 12h respectively because it contains higher amount of HPMC (100mg, 125mg and 150mg resp.) which retarded the release of drug for more than 12 h. As these formulation F₇, F₈ and F₉ retarded the release of Propranolol HCl for more than 12 hrs therefore, these formulation were not satisfying criteria. Based on highest percentage of release i.e. 97.12±2.47% in 12 h and other evaluation parameters Formulation F₃ was designated as optimized batch.

Kinetic Treatment:

Formulations containing cordia exhibited zero order drug release kinetics with R² value >0.99. The 'n' value of formulation F₃ from Korsmeyer-Peppas equation was found to be 1.057 indicating that the release mechanism was super case II release (n > 1). It showed that the release was dependent on both drug diffusion and polymer erosion.

Stability Study:

The optimized batches F₃ was kept for stability study, which showed insignificant change in *in-vitro* drug release and other evaluation parameters for the period of 6 months at 40°C/75% RH.

CONCLUSION

Sustained release mucoadhesive tablet of Propranolol HCl was successfully prepared using biopolymers by wet granulation method. Tablets were evaluated for weight variation, hardness, friability, drug content, swelling index, erosion study, *in-vitro* drug release and *in-vitro* mucoadhesion study. It was revealed that tablets of all batches had acceptable physical parameters. FT-IR studies stated that there is no interaction between drug and biopolymers used in the tablet. Nature and concentration of biopolymer were found to be important parameters affecting the drug release, mucoadhesion and swelling behavior of tablets. The tablets of batch F₃ prepared using Cordia mucilage(150mg) had better ability to sustained the release drug for 12 hrs and showed good mucoadhesive strength than other formulations. Thus, the results of the present study demonstrated that the Cordia biopolymer can be used as a drug release retardant and mucoadhesive biomaterial for formulation of mucoadhesive drug delivery systems.

REFERENCES

1. Siddique S, Khan MY, Verma CJ, Pal TK, Khanam J. Formulation of sustained release matrix system of highly water soluble drugs Pharm Rev. 2008.
2. Banker GS, Rhodes CT, Modern Pharmaceutics. 3rd ed. Marcel Dekker, New York, 1979; 575.
3. Madan J, Banode S, Dangi M, Mucosal Drug Delivery System, International Journal of Research in Ayurveda & Pharmacy, 01(1); 2010, pp 63-70.
4. Nakano M, Nakamura Y, Juni K. Sustained release of sulfamethizole from agar beads after oral administration to humans. Chem Pharm Bull. 1980; 28: 2905-2908.
5. Durso DF. Handbook of Water Soluble Gums and Resins. New York, NY: McGraw Hill, Kingsport Press. 1980; p. 12.
6. Bhardwaj TR, Kanwar M, Lal R. Natural gums and modified natural gums as sustained release carriers. Drug Dev Ind Pharm. 2000; 26: 1025-1038.
7. Desai A, Shidhaye S, Malke S. Use of natural release retardant in drug delivery system. Indian Drugs J. 2005; 42: 565-575.
8. Patil ND, Marathe RP, Patil KS. Extraction and characterization of mucilages from fruits of *Cordia latifolia* and *Aegle marmelos* for its mucoadhesive behavior. Indo Am J of Pharma Res, Vol 8 (01), 2018, 1257-1266.
9. P Patil, SV Kulkarni, S Rao B, A Ammanage, C Surpur, Basavaraj. Formulation and *in-vitro* evaluation of mucoadhesive tablets of ofloxacin using natural gums. Int J Curr Pharm Res, Vol 3, Issue 2, 93-98.
10. Indian Pharmacopoeia, Government of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Controller of Publication, New Delhi, 2007; vol-1:36-37.
11. Lachman L, Liberman HA, Kanig LJ. The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy. 3rd ed. 1991; 430-431, 67-69, 296-302, 316-318, 320-321.
12. Malvia R, Shrivastav P, Bansal V, Sharma PK. Formulation, evaluation and comparison of sustained release matrix tablet of Diclofenac sodium using natural polymer as release modifier. Int J Pharm Bio-Sci. 2010; 1 (2): 1-8.

13. Basavaraj RS, Kulkarni SV, Patil P, Surpur C. Design and characterization of sustained release aceclofenac matrix tablet containing Tamarind seed polysaccharide. Asian J Pharm Tech. 2011; 1(1): 17-21.
14. Kulkarni GT, Seshubabu P, Siddaiah MK. Effect of Tamarind seed polysaccharide on dissolution behavior of ibuprofen tablet. J Chronotherapy Drug Del. 2011; 2 (1): 49-56.
15. Jain GK, Shah DP. Evaluation of mucilage of *Hibiscus rosasinesis Linn* as a rate controlling matrix for sustain release of diclofenac, Drug Dev Ind Pharm. 2008; 807-816.
16. Reddy MM, Reddy JD, Moin A, Shivakumar HG. Formulation of sustained-release matrix tablets using cross-linked Karaya gum. Trop J Pharm Res. 2012; 11 (2): 185-192.
17. Rathi PC, Bundela MN, Patil KS, Yeole PG. Design and characterization of propranolol HCl tablet containing tamarind seed polysaccharide as a release retardant. International Journal of Institutional Pharmacy and Life Sciences 2013;3(2),1-11.
18. Lalla JK, Gurnancy RA. Polymers for mucosal delivery-swelling and mucoadhesive delivery. Indian Drugs 2002; 39:270-276
19. Gupta A, Garg S, Khar RK. Measurement of bioadhesive strength of mucoadhesive buccal tablets: design of an in vitro assembly. Indian Drugs 1993; 36:110-26.
20. Ali J, Khar R, Ahuja A, Karla R. Buccoadhesive erodible disk for treatment of orodental infections design and characterization. Int. J. Pharm, 283; 2002:93-103.
21. International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH), Guidance for industry QIA (R2) Stability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products; 2003.

54878478451181002

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **Scopus** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

